

Digital Twin for Battery Systems: Review and Conceptual Hybrid Modeling Framework

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Abstract—This paper presents a structured approach to designing and implementing a digital twin (DT) for lithium-ion battery (LIB) systems. We reviewed current DT applications in battery management, focusing on real-time estimation of state-of-charge (SoC) and state-of-health (SoH), thermal analysis, and lifecycle monitoring. Modeling techniques are categorized into physics-based, equivalent circuit, and data-driven models, emphasizing their integration into hybrid digital twin architectures.

A conceptual DT framework is proposed that integrates real-time measurements with simulation through edge computing and commercially available platforms. This architecture allows computationally intensive tasks to be offloaded from the battery management system (BMS), enabling scalable, real-time diagnostics and control. The presented concept serves as a foundation for practical implementation of battery digital twins in electric vehicles and stationary storage systems.

Index Terms—Digital Twin, Lithium-Ion Battery, Battery Management System, Parameter Estimation, Hybrid Modeling.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
EV	Electric Vehicle
DT	Digital Twin
BMS	Battery Management System
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Health
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Model
DDM	Data Driven Model
ROM	Reduced-Order Model
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
LIB	Lithium-Ion Battery

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I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation electrification plays a key role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating climate change. Electric vehicles (EVs), which rely on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) as their main power source, play a pivotal role in this transition. However, LIBs present numerous operational and lifecycle challenges such as degradation, high cost, complex thermal management, and safety concerns arising from thermal runaway or overcharging [1], [2].

Battery Management Systems (BMS) are essential for monitoring, protecting, and optimizing battery usage. Traditional BMS, however, are typically limited by low-cost hardware and constrained algorithms, preventing advanced functionality like accurate state estimation or degradation prediction [3], [4]. To address these challenges, the Digital Twin (DT) concept has been introduced as an integration of physical assets and their virtual counterparts.

The concept of a Digital Twin was first introduced in the aerospace industry (NASA, 2010) to track complex physical systems over time. It has since evolved with the rise of IoT, AI, and cloud technologies [1]. A battery Digital Twin (DT) is a dynamic, continuously updated digital representation of a physical battery system. It integrates high-fidelity models, real-time sensor data, and historical usage data using machine learning, artificial intelligence, and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies [4], [5]. This allows for real-time monitoring, diagnosis, prediction, and control of battery systems. The differences between a digital model, digital shadow, and digital twin are illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Difference between battery model, digital shadow, and DT [1].

Several research works [2], [4]–[6] have emphasized the applicability of DTs in supporting enhanced functionalities within smart BMS, particularly by enabling:

- Real-time estimation of state-of-charge (SoC), state-of-health (SoH), and remaining useful life (RUL).
- Inputs for thermal and charging optimization strategies.
- Model-based analysis of degradation mechanisms.
- Second-life performance assessment.
- Lifecycle data integration through digital battery passports.

Additionally, DTs are capable of fusing model-driven and data-driven approaches for more accurate system behaviour estimation, enabling faster response to operational changes and safety events [2], [7]. As a result, DTs are increasingly seen as a core enabler of intelligent battery lifecycle management.

Battery DT technology offers distinct advantages in several critical dimensions [1]:

- **Application:** Enhances battery design optimization, improves operational efficiency and maintenance, and extends battery lifespan, leading to cost-effective solutions.
- **Emissions and Environment:** Facilitates the adoption of clean energy technologies, supports environmental sustainability initiatives, and aids in achieving UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Policy Targets:** Enables comprehensive tracking of battery performance over its lifetime, supporting policy objectives in energy storage, emissions reduction, and sustainability.
- **Regulation and Standards:** Accelerates the standardization and regulations for battery safety and performance.
- **Cost:** Reduces the life cycle costs by improving manufacturing efficiency, decreasing maintenance expenses, and extending battery service life.

Despite significant progress in academic research, practical implementation of battery DTs remains a challenge, especially in industrial contexts where requirements for system integration, standardization, and computational efficiency are often underestimated [5], [6]. There is also a need for clearer architectural frameworks and scalable deployment strategies, particularly for embedded use in smart BMS systems.

This work aims to consolidate the state of knowledge on battery DT technology and explore how it can be effectively integrated within the BMS domain. It further proposes a conceptual design of a battery DT suitable for real-time operation and SoC/SoH estimation. Framework of a battery DT is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Framework of a battery digital twin [4].

II. USE CASES OF BATTERY DIGITAL TWINS IN OPERATION

This section outlines the key functional domains where battery digital twins are actively applied and demonstrate the greatest potential for impact.

A. *SOC and SOH Estimation*

State-of-Charge (SoC) and State-of-Health (SoH) estimation are among the most critical tasks in battery management. Traditional BMS approaches often rely on simplified models or Kalman filters with limited adaptability. In contrast, Digital Twins enable the fusion of high-fidelity physical models with machine learning-based estimators, enhancing accuracy under dynamic conditions. In [4] the authors propose a DT framework combining real-time sensor data with geometric, thermal, and aging models to improve SoC and SoH estimation. The paper [2] highlights the benefit of hybrid modeling, where a digital twin continuously adapts to operational feedback through AI techniques. Furthermore, [5] demonstrate that this integration enables better responsiveness and longer battery life by updating internal states in real time.

B. *Fault Diagnosis and Predictive Maintenance*

Battery systems are prone to faults such as over-temperature, over-voltage, or internal short circuits. Digital Twins provide a platform for real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance through continuous comparison of expected vs. measured behaviors. Vandana et al. [7] emphasize the DT's role in fault identification by simulating deviations in thermal and electrical characteristics. Singh et al. [5] describe how predictive models in the DT can anticipate failure modes and trigger preventive actions. This proactive maintenance strategy significantly enhances safety and system uptime.

C. *Charging Optimization, Thermal Monitoring, and Cell Balancing*

Optimizing the charging profile and managing internal temperature distribution are crucial to extend battery life and ensure safe operation. Wang et al. [4] present how DT-based BMS can dynamically control charge/discharge rates and cooling strategies in response to real-time battery conditions. Wu et al. [2] show that DTs support adaptive strategies by modeling thermal propagation and electrical imbalance between cells. These insights enable more effective thermal management and automated balancing, improving both performance and safety.

D. *RUL Estimation and Second Life Assessment*

Accurate estimation of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) is vital for decision-making in electric vehicle fleets and stationary storage. Digital Twins integrate degradation models with operational data, enabling robust RUL prediction. Bhatti et al. [3] and Wu et al. [2] discuss methods for leveraging usage history and physics-informed modeling to forecast degradation. This is especially relevant for second-life applications, where DTs can evaluate whether aged batteries remain viable for lower-power use cases.

E. *Battery Passport and Lifecycle Digitalization*

The concept of a digital battery passport is increasingly important for traceability, recycling, and regulatory compliance. Wu et al. [2] and Bhatti et al. [3] position DTs as the backbone of such passports by capturing historical data across the battery's lifecycle—from manufacturing through usage to end-of-life. Vandana et al. [7] additionally propose a lifecycle-oriented DT structure supporting recycling decisions and environmental reporting. This digitalization facilitates transparency, promotes sustainability, and aligns with global battery passport initiatives.

III. MODELING APPROACHES AND HYBRID ARCHITECTURES FOR BATTERY DIGITAL TWINS

Battery digital twins often combine detailed multiphysics models with simplified, lightweight models to balance fidelity and speed. These modeling approaches can be broadly categorized into physics-based models, equivalent circuit models (ECM), and data-driven models (DDM). High-fidelity simulations provide deep insight into battery behavior, while reduced-order and empirical models support real-time performance. Digital twins often integrate these approaches, enhanced by model order reduction and hybrid frameworks, to enable accurate, adaptive, and computationally efficient systems [8].

A. *Standard Battery Modeling Approaches*

1) *Physics-Based Models*: Physics-based models in the context of battery systems refer to those derived from first-principles laws of nature, including either electrochemical and thermal processes, or both.

Electrochemical models, like the Doyle–Fuller–Newman (DFN) model, simulate the lithium-ion transport within electrode particles and electrolytes, electrochemical reactions at interfaces, and overpotentials. These models are highly accurate and can capture complex internal dynamics but are computationally expensive. In contrast, Single Particle Models (SPM) offer a simplified alternative by representing the active material with a single spherical particle per electrode. The work by Bhatti et al. [3] and the recent study in Applied Energy by S.M. Jordan et al. [9] highlight the use of such electrochemical models in digital twin applications, especially when combined with degradation or aging models.

Thermal models aim to estimate the spatial and temporal temperature distribution within a battery cell or pack. These range from simple lumped models (e.g., 1D or 2D) to full 3D computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models. The paper [10] demonstrates a validated CFD approach using COMSOL to capture thermal gradients under forced convection. Similarly, in the work [9], volume-averaged 3D CFD simulations are used to predict local hot spots and evaluate cooling efficiency. Both electrochemical and thermal models are frequently combined in multiphysics frameworks for more realistic digital twin implementations. These physics-based models provide foundational accuracy and their reduced-order forms are often used in real-time digital twin systems.

2) **Equivalent Circuit Models (ECM):** Equivalent circuit models (ECMs) are among the most widely used approaches in battery management systems due to their simplicity and computational efficiency. These models approximate the dynamic behavior of batteries using electrical components such as resistors (R), capacitors (C), and voltage sources. Common configurations include Thevenin-type models, such as the 1RC and 2RC variants, where each RC branch captures time-dependent voltage relaxation and polarization effects. These models typically include an internal resistance and open-circuit voltage defined as functions of the state of charge (SoC) [1], [11].

ECMs are typically developed through system identification techniques, where parameters are extracted from experimental data (e.g., current pulse tests). They are well-suited for real-time applications such as SoC and SoH estimation, state prediction, and fault diagnosis. For example, the paper [12] integrates a 2RC circuit with an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) in a MATLAB/Simulink environment, showing its applicability in embedded digital twin systems for EVs. The model is validated against real driving profiles and demonstrates robustness in real-time tracking. 1-RC ECM can be seen in Figure 3.

Additionally, ECMs can be extended to model thermal behavior using lumped thermal analogues—replacing electrical components with their thermal equivalents. This is shown in the thermal modeling review [13], where Cauer-type networks are used to estimate temperature distribution in cylindrical cells. Despite their limitations in physical interpretability and accuracy under extreme conditions, ECMs remain a cornerstone of battery DTs due to their ease of integration, adaptability, and low computational demand.

Fig. 3. The electrical structure of 1-RC ECM [11].

3) **Data-Driven Models:** Data-driven models (DDMs) use machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques to predict battery behavior based on historical and real-time data, bypassing the need for detailed physical modeling. These approaches are particularly useful when internal battery states are not directly measurable or when modeling complex degradation behavior that is difficult to capture using traditional physics-based models [1].

Supervised learning approaches such as artificial neural networks, support vector machines, and decision trees have been widely used for tasks including state-of-health (SoH) estimation, remaining useful life (RUL) prediction, and fault detection. Recurrent neural networks and long short-term memory networks are particularly effective in modeling time-series data for dynamic SoC and temperature estimation — as demonstrated in the work by Wu et al. [2], which emphasizes the fusion of data and AI in battery digital twins.

Furthermore, Convolutional Neural Network based architectures have been applied to estimate spatial temperature distributions across battery cells, and autoencoders have been used to extract latent features for early fault prediction [13]. These approaches demonstrate the potential of DDMs not only for prediction, but also for system-level optimization and diagnostics.

Despite their power, data-driven models require high-quality and representative datasets to be effective and are sensitive to overfitting if not properly regularized. Their black-box nature limits physical interpretability, which is why hybrid approaches that fuse DDMs with physics-based models are increasingly preferred to enhance robustness and generalization capability [1].

The advantages and limitations of commonly used modeling techniques for battery digital twins are summarized in Figure 4.

Model	Pros	Cons
Equivalent circuit models	Widely used for SoX estimation, a nice trade-off between accuracy and complexity, error lower than 2% achievable	Parameterization requires special types of tests at different temperatures and SoC conditions Poor interpretation of battery physics
Electrochemical model	High accuracy, Ability to track the aging of battery components, e.g., the thickness of the solid electrolyte interphase, Models the physics of battery	Prior knowledge of battery required, Manufacturing and construction data needed, Time-consuming training process, High computational burden
Data-driven	Does not require prior knowledge about the cell, Strong mapping potential	Collecting the training datasets in the laboratory is very time-consuming and costly
Empirical $V_{battery} = f(\text{SoC}, I, T)$	Simple representation, Minimum complexity	Low accuracy

Fig. 4. Comparison of different modeling techniques for battery DT [1].

B. Hybrid Battery Modeling Architectures

Hybrid modeling architectures represent a convergence of the modeling techniques described in Section 3.1 — most often combining physics-based models (e.g., electrochemical or thermal), ECMs, DDMs into a unified framework. This integrated approach addresses the trade-off between accuracy and computational tractability, which is critical for real-time operation in digital twin systems.

A notable example is the use of 3D CFD thermal models in conjunction with ECMs. For example, the study by Jordan et al. [9] demonstrates a hybrid setup using COMSOL Multiphysics to simulate spatial temperature distributions across a battery pack, while integrating it with a reduced-order ECM

for fast SoC and SoH estimation. This combination allows for accurate thermal diagnostics while maintaining computational speed.

Similarly, the [10] publication presents a hybrid CFD-thermal model validated using experimental calorimetry. The CFD block predicts airflow and convection around battery cells, and the resulting temperature data is fed into control algorithms running on equivalent RC networks. The ROM techniques applied to the CFD results further enhance usability in embedded or cloud-based digital twin systems.

Ansys Twin Builder is a powerful platform that facilitates this type of integration. It allows users to import ROM-exported CFD models (e.g., from Fluent) and connect them with ECM. These models can then be fed with real-time operational data for continuous calibration and prediction. As described by Rajesh et al. [14], such a setup supports online diagnostics, aging tracking, and safety control, especially in EV battery packs.

Another hybrid approach includes fusing data-driven algorithms with physics-based or ECM models. For instance, machine learning methods can be used to continuously update model parameters or to estimate unmeasured states (e.g., SoH) based on real-time sensor inputs. The article by Bilansky et al. [12] highlights how an Extended Kalman Filter bridges measured data with a 2RC model, demonstrating predictive accuracy over varied duty cycles.

In summary, hybrid architectures capitalize on the complementary strengths of different modeling paradigms. They enable accurate, scalable, and flexible digital twin systems that adapt to dynamic operational conditions, offering a realistic pathway toward deployable and intelligent battery management in electric vehicles and stationary applications.

IV. CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF A BATTERY DIGITAL TWIN SYSTEM

The previous sections outlined the motivations for battery digital twin implementation, the areas of application, and the available modeling techniques. In this section we propose a conceptual framework for a digital twin that integrates real-time data acquisition with hybrid model architecture. To enable real-time, model-informed battery monitoring and diagnostics, we propose a digital twin architecture that couples a physical battery system with a high-fidelity virtual model running in Ansys Twin Builder. The system comprises three main layers: the physical sensing and acquisition layer, the communication and edge-processing layer, and the simulation and control layer.

At the physical level, sensors embedded in the battery module collect real-time operational data and send them to the BMS. These data are passed to an edge device — such as a Raspberry Pi — which serves as a lightweight intermediary between the hardware and the virtual environment. The edge device aggregates, preprocesses and transmits the sensor data to the simulation layer, allowing the use of a simplified BMS focused solely on data acquisition rather than complex onboard computation.

Ansys Twin Builder supports integration with a wide range of IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) platforms, including Microsoft Azure IoT, PTC ThingWorx, and SAP Predictive Asset Insights, enabling seamless connectivity with industrial systems and external data sources. This flexibility allows for communication between edge devices and the Twin Builder environment. In this context, communication between the edge device and Twin Builder can be realized through supported IoT connectors or middleware. Twin Builder, operating on a dedicated computational node or server, receives the live data stream and feeds it into a pre-configured simulation composed

Fig. 5. System simulation steps of battery DT in the Ansys Twin Builder [15].

of a reduced-order CFD thermal model and an equivalent circuit model (ECM). These models estimate the state of charge (SoC), state of health (SoH), and potentially predict thermal hotspots or degradation trends. Ansys Twin Builder DT scheme is illustrated in Figure 5. [15].

The estimated states and predictions can then be visualized locally on the edge device. Additionally, a feedback channel can be implemented to communicate critical model-informed recommendations (e.g., limiting charge current, activating cooling systems) back to the BMS.

This modular architecture is scalable and allows the separation of heavy computation from embedded control, making it suitable for practical deployment in electric vehicle systems or laboratory-grade battery test environments. The final concept can be seen in Figure 6. As illustrated in Figure 6, the directional arrows indicate the flow of information between the physical and virtual components. One-way arrows represent real-time data acquisition from the battery system, while the two-way-arrows represent bidirectional data and feedback channels that can be used for closed-loop control.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a structured review and conceptual framework for implementing digital twins in lithium-ion battery systems, with particular emphasis on their application in

battery management. Through the categorization of existing modeling techniques—physics-based, equivalent circuit, and data-driven—we highlight their individual strengths and the added value of hybrid architectures for real-time diagnostics and control.

The proposed framework integrates real-time sensor data with simulation environments via edge computing, enabling scalable deployment while reducing the computational burden on embedded battery management systems. This modular approach leverages commercially available tools and supports the estimation of critical states such as SoC, SoH, and temperature distribution.

The work serves as a foundation for future development of operational digital twin platforms capable of supporting predictive maintenance, optimization, and lifecycle tracking. As the field progresses, digital twins will become essential enablers of safe, efficient, and intelligent battery systems for both electric vehicles and stationary storage applications.

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Fig. 6. Conceptual architecture of a hybrid digital twin, integrating edge computing with physics-based and ECM simulation.

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